

Research

Design and Research on The Simulation of Motion for Industrial Robotic Arm

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Abstract: Presently, the global landscape is being transformed by the rapid adoption of cutting-edge technologies like 5G communication, big data, AI, and virtual reality. This digital revolution has led to the flourishing of new technologies and industries worldwide. This article performs forward and inverse kinematics analysis and joint space trajectory planning for industrial robotic arms. The planned results are then imported into the Unity3D platform to simulate the motion of the robotic arm in a virtual system. The robotic arm's physical structure allows it to accurately replicate the movement of the actual robotic arm during operation. It can also anticipate potential hazards along its path, ensuring safety and providing a basis for future research on obstacle avoidance planning for robotic arms.

Keywords: Industrial robotic arm; Digital twin; Motion control

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Introduction

Currently, the digital wave represented by emerging technologies such as 5G communication technology, big data, AI technology, and virtual reality has swept the world, and global new technologies and industries are flourishing. Industrial robotic arms are crucial equipment in the field of intelligent manufacturing. Their research and development, production, manufacturing, and application are important indicators for measuring a country's advanced manufacturing level and technological innovation ability, as well as an important strategic direction for achieving high-quality development of the manufacturing industry. Its internal structure is very complex, integrating various advanced technologies such as computers, sensors, control engineering, and image processing, and includes multiple subsystems, providing necessary scientific and regulatory support for the all-round performance of industrial robotic arms. Therefore, robotic arms are widely used in large-scale repetitive work and high risk situations.

Due to the fact that most industrial robotic arms interact with humans or the environment to complete their work, if there is a sudden change in the working environment or collision with obstacles, it not only causes economic losses to the enterprise, but may even pose a threat to the safety of workers. Therefore, real-time monitoring of the operation

status of the robotic arm can not only timely detect problems that occur during the working process of the robotic arm, but also improve the production efficiency of the enterprise and ensure smooth and safe operation during the task. Monitoring is an important management method in the working process of robotic arms. Managers need to be familiar with the real-time operation status of the robotic arm in order to comprehensively monitor it, identify and solve problems in a timely manner, and avoid accidents. This not only improves the monitoring efforts of managers, but also strengthens the work efficiency of the robotic arm. Both domestic and foreign enterprises and researchers have made progress in motion simulation and real-time monitoring of industrial robotic arms

Most robot simulation platforms have a low level of intelligence and compatibility, and some platforms may restrict language programming, which is too cumbersome. Some robots may not have high motion accuracy. In addition, the viewing experience of the simulation platform is inconsistent with the actual platform, resulting in users being unable to immerse themselves and experiencing a tearing sensation.

The monitoring method for robotic arms is single and not transparent enough. Nowadays, most factories use video surveillance to observe the operation status of robotic arms, but this method has problems such as poor visual effects, poor interaction, and blind spots in monitoring, which cause considerable difficulties for the comprehensive monitoring of robotic arms. In terms of managing the operation data of the robotic arm, it is difficult to review the historical data of the robotic arm, which is not conducive to later maintenance organization and further development research.

In response to the above shortcomings, this article conducts research on the monitoring of robotic arm status based on digital twin technology. Digital twin is a technology that integrates multiple physical quantities, interdisciplinary attributes, and scales to accelerate the integration of digital information technology and intelligent economy. The trend of industrial informatization and intelligence evolution is becoming increasingly evident.

2. Literature Review

There is no clear explanation for the origin of the concept of Digital Twin. Many people believe that it originated from NASA's Apollo program. The goal of this plan is to create two identical spacecraft, one launched into space and the other left on the ground to reflect their operational status, known as twins. At this time, the "twin" is still a real physical entity [1]. In 2002, American professor Michael Grieves first proposed the PLM conceptual model. The model includes real space, virtual space, as well as data flow and information transmission between the two, and this conceptual model is also considered the prototype of digital twins [2]. In 2005, Professor Michael referred to the PLM conceptual model as the "Information Mirror Model" in his published work. In 2011, Michael Grieves cited the concept of digital twins proposed by collaborator John in his book "Almost Perfect: Driving Innovation and Lean Products through Product Lifecycle Management" [3], which has been used to this day.

In 2012, the American Institute of Standards and Technology proposed a leap from MBD (Model Based Definition) to MBE (Model Based Enterprise) [4]. The key is to integrate virtual models into various fields and aspects of enterprise production. One creation can provide convenience for subsequent product manufacturing, services, and other aspects [5]. In 2012, NASA defined digital twin as a simulation process that integrates multiple physical quantities and spatial scales. This simulation fully utilizes the most effective physical models, sensor updates, historical data, etc., reflecting the state of twin objects [6]. From then on, companies such as Microsoft in the United States and Siemens in Germany have successively applied digital twins to technology development and production research, forming software development platforms such as Predix platform and Siemens 3D, which have attracted widespread attention from domestic and foreign industries, academia, and media [7]. Chen Zhen et al. studied a new production model for aircraft assembly workshops, based on digital twin technology, collecting and transmitting physical data of the assembly workshop, constructing a virtual assembly workshop, achieving interconnection and interoperability, and providing reference for the field of intelligent manufacturing in the aerospace industry [8]. Tao Fei and others from Beihang University proposed the concept of digital twin workshop, systematically explained the composition and operation mechanism of the workshop and proposed a four-dimensional structural model of the digital workshop, providing

theoretical support for the application of digital twin production and manufacturing [9]. Zhuang Cunbo et al. elaborated on the definition of digital twins, predicted the future development and development of products, and proposed the concept of product digital twins. By digitizing the entire process of design, manufacturing, and production, efficiency levels can be improved to new heights.

3. Method and Model

3.1 Robot Arm Motion Simulation

Building a robotic arm state monitoring simulation system on the Uniyt3D platform, the process of robotic arm state monitoring simulation is as follows:

Design target points. The target point is the designated location that the robotic arm needs to reach when performing work tasks. Users need to design the target position of the robotic arm based on the task it needs to complete. Taking the glass handling robotic arm in this article as an example, the target point of the robotic arm is the endpoint position of the arm when completing a glass handling task, as well as the position and posture of the end suction cup holder.

Solve the trajectory planning results. According to the target point given by the user, the forward and inverse kinematics analysis of the manipulator is carried out, and the trajectory planning results of the manipulator are solved. The obtained trajectory planning results are imported into Unity3D, and this method is called to make the model realize the same trajectory movement.

Conduct simulation analysis. In Unity3D, the results obtained from the trajectory planning are simulated, and the algorithm is called during the movement of the manipulator. When the manipulator finds obstacles in the running process, it will remind the user, facilitate the user to adjust, and ensure the safety and stability of the manipulator in the working process.

Output results and control motion. Output the calculated trajectory planning results and transmit the data to the controller to control the motion of the robotic arm body. Obtaining target points in a virtual environment can reduce the time spent on on-site operations for users, without being limited by time and space.

It can be seen from the process of simulating and monitoring a robotic arm that kinematic analysis and trajectory planning analysis are essential to achieve the movement of the robotic arm in a virtual environment. The following will provide a specific introduction to them.

3.2 Fundamentals of Kinematics

For the description of robots in space, position and attitude can be used to define them, but how to define and apply numerical quantities that express position and attitude, we need to first define a coordinate system. After establishing the coordinate system, we can use a position vector to represent any point in the world coordinate system, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Vector description relative to the coordinate system

After representing points in space, it is also necessary to describe the posture of objects in space. The method used to describe the posture of an object is to create a virtual coordinate system, which is located on the body of the object. Then, the description of this coordinate system relative to other coordinate systems is represented, which is the posture of the object. Assuming that the coordinate system {B} is fixed on an object, the description of the {B} coordinate system relative to the {A} coordinate system is the posture of the object in the {A} coordinate system, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Description of object's attitude

3.3 Model Design Process

Based on the analysis of the above four design requirements, the specific virtual system construction process is as follows:

Model drawing

SolidWorks software is the world's first mechanical 3D design tool software developed by Microsoft, suitable for the electrical industry design [40]. It uses SolidWorks software to draw models of various parts of a robotic arm. The 3D models in virtual environments mainly include the main assembly of robotic arms, control boxes, and other equipment. Draw models of various parts of the robotic arm in SolidWorks software. Taking the monitoring subject in the virtual environment used in this study, a five axis glass handling robotic arm, as an example, the robotic arm mainly includes six parts: column assembly, X-axis assembly, Y-axis assembly, Z-axis assembly, flipping axis assembly, and suction cup holder assembly. Draw the part models of these six parts separately in SolidWorks software and draw the part models of these six parts in sequence, as shown in Figure 3.

(a) Model of Column Assembly Parts; (b) X-axis assembly part model; (c) Y-axis assembly part model; (d) Z-axis assembly part model; (e) Flip axis assembly part model; (f) Model of suction cup holder assembly parts

Figure 3 Assembly model of various parts of the robotic arm

Since the assembly model drawn by SolidWorks is in SLDASM format, but Unty3D software does not support direct import of this format, it is necessary to use the intermediate software 3DsMax for format conversion. First, convert the assembly model drawn by SolidWorks to STL format, and then use 3DsMax software to convert the STL format model to FBX format [41]. The specific steps are as follows:

Firstly, save the parts models of the robotic arm drawn by SolidWorks software to STL format files. STL (Stereo Lithography) file is a file format used in computer-aided design software to represent triangular meshes, which can be used to represent 3D and CAD models. An STL file is composed of various small triangular patches and can be used to approximate the surface of a 3D model. The definition of each triangle patch includes the three-dimensional coordinates of each vertex of the triangle and the normal vector of the triangle patch, but it can only represent the geometric shape of the model surface, without colors, materials, and so on.

Secondly, import the STL format file into the 3DsMax software and save it as an FBX format file. FBX format is one of the main 3D exchange file formats, which integrates almost all material properties, animation information, texture information, lighting, camera, and other information. FBX format files have great compatibility with 3D software, and almost all 3D software supports importing FBX format models, so FBX format can interact with different 3D software. Due to the existence of many 3D part models for robotic arms in virtual environments, the models themselves contain a large number of topological structures, namely, many points, lines, and surfaces. For users, the more points, lines, and surfaces a model contains, the clearer the external texture of the model, which can provide users with a more realistic experience. However, the presence of a large number of points, lines, and surfaces in the model can cause great pressure on the system's operation, greatly prolonging the model loading time and reducing work efficiency.

So a reasonable approach is to reduce unnecessary points, lines, and surfaces in the model, reduce the burden on the system, and improve the smoothness of system operation while ensuring that it does not harm the customer's visual experience. Therefore, it is necessary to perform lightweight processing on the model, while ensuring that the detailed features of the model do not disappear and the model does not deform, and appropriately reducing the number of points, lines, and surfaces modeled. By using the built-in MultiRes modifier in the 3DsMax software, optimization can be achieved by changing the vertex scale of the model, accelerating the interaction speed of the model on the computer. The optimized results of the number of vertices and faces in the model are shown in Table 1

Table 1 Optimization Results of Model Vertex and Face Numbers

Optimization items	Number of vertices	Number of faces	Optimized number of vertices	Optimize the following numbers
Column assembly model	5563	11334	1268	2744
X-axis assembly model	27071	60374	5415	12074
Y-axis assembly model	13093	30792	2618	6158

Z-axis assembly model	22556	45920	4000	9100
Flip axis assembly model	167476	33539	33500	67078
Assembly model of suction cup holder	130866	262232	32716	65558

4. Kinematic Results and Analysis

To analyze the trajectory of a robotic arm, the first step is to solve the forward and inverse kinematics of the arm and study the mutual conversion of kinematic parameters between joint space and Cartesian space. This section will introduce the forward and inverse kinematics analysis of robots. Firstly, establish the D-H parameter table of the robotic arm; Then, based on the D-H parameter table, obtain the forward and inverse solutions of the robotic arm; Finally, using the results of forward and inverse kinematics, trajectory planning is performed on the robotic arm.

This article takes a five axis glass handling robotic arm as the research object, which has 5 degrees of freedom, including 3 movable joints and 2 rotating joint axes. The assembly of X, Y, and Z axes can realize the movement of the robotic arm in the X, Y, and Z directions, while the rotating axis enables the suction cup to rotate counterclockwise or clockwise around the Z axis; The flipping axis realizes the counterclockwise or clockwise rotation of the suction cup around the axis of the flipping axis, completing the flipping action of the suction cup. The structure of the robotic arm is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Five axis glass handling robotic arm

Based on the above analysis, establish the coordinate system structure of the linkage of the robotic arm, as shown in Figure 5. Then analyze and study the changes in the position and posture of the suction cup holder at the end of the robotic arm.

Figure 5 Coordinate System of the Connecting Rod of the Robot Arm

Based on the above analysis of the coordinate system of the robotic arm, a D-H table can be drawn, as shown in Table 2. According to the D-H parameter table, kinematic analysis of the robotic arm can be performed.

Table 2 Robot D-H Parameter Table

i	$i 1 (^{\circ})$	$ai 1 (mm)$	$di (mm)$	$i (^{\circ})$
1	0	0	d1	0
2	90	0	d2	90
3	-90	0	d3	0
4	0	0	d4	4
5	90	0	d5	5

The forward kinematics of a robotic arm involves calculating the position and orientation of the end effector assembly relative to the base coordinate system, given the angles of each joint axis of the robotic arm. And inverse kinematics is to solve the angle problem of each joint axis given the position and posture of the end effector of the robotic arm. The solution of inverse kinematics is the basis for trajectory planning of robotic arms. By giving the position and attitude of the suction cup holder at the end of the robotic arm, the path, velocity, and other parameters for the robotic arm to reach the target point can be obtained. The methods for solving are mainly divided into analytical methods and numerical methods. Numerical methods have the characteristic of wide applicability, but the solving process requires a large amount of computation, and problems such as numerical error accumulation and matrix singularity may occur during the calculation, leading to solution failure.

5. Conclusion

Conduct forward and inverse kinematics analysis as well as trajectory planning for the robotic arm. Integrate trajectory planning algorithms into a virtual system to simulate the motion of the robotic arm model. Simultaneously, a human-machine interface was developed to monitor the status of the robotic arm. This interface displays the operational data of the robotic arm within the system. Ultimately, the algorithm's effectiveness was demonstrated through trajectory planning simulation experiments.

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